

ELECTRODIALYSIS OF SOILS. THE INFLUENCE OF EXCHANGEABLE BASES ON THE RECOVERY OF MANGANESE BY ELECTRODIALYSIS.

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Soils containing manganese and one of the elements viz., Na, K, Ca and Mg were electrolysed and the manganese, both in the electrolysate and the deposit on the cathode etc., was separately determined. As the result of this study, the effect of different bases which may be present in the exchange complex of soils on the recovery of manganese is brought out.

A few natural soils have been subjected to electrolysis and the manganese in the electrolysate determined. Bad soils yield greater amount of manganese in the electrolysable form than soils with low p_H values.

It is concluded that at high p_H values when, the dominant base in the exchange complex of soils is sodium, more manganese comes out in the soluble form and is thus made available to plants. This availability of manganese to plants may be reduced when the dominant base in the exchange complex of soils is calcium or magnesium.

The importance of trace elements in the soil in influencing plant nutrition is gradually being realised. It is well known that replaceable or electrolysable bases are more readily available to plants than the non-replaceable ones. The estimation of these bases by electrolysis has been recommended by several workers (S. Mattson, *Soil Sci.*, 1938, 45, 309; Prince and Toth, *ibid.*, 1938, 46, 83; Puri and Hoon, *ibid.*, 1936, 43, 305). This method has been recently applied to study the antagonism between sodium and calcium in soils (Puri, Hoon and Dhawan, *Soil Sci.*, 1939, 47, 479). As the replaceable bases appear as hydroxides on electrolysis, manganese occupies a peculiar position in so far as its hydroxide is sparingly soluble in water. Thus not only it will have a tendency to be deposited on the cathode but the presence of other bases will exercise an influence on the manner of its recovery by electrolysis. Prince and Toth (*loc. cit.*) by using soils partially saturated with manganese, recently studied the effect of lime on exchangeable and electrolysable manganese. They found that with the increase of lime applications the exchangeable manganese decreased.

The object of the present investigation was to study the extent to which the recovery of manganese from soils by electrolysis might be affected by the presence of other bases in the exchange complex.

E X P E R I M E N T A L.

Preparation of Soils.

(i) Three soils were selected for this study. Soil No. P.C. 13 was a black cotton soil of high exchange capacity. Soil No. P.C. 72 was an alluvial clayey loam and soil No. P.C. 123 was a raw alluvial clayey sub-soil containing 83 % of clay. The following table gives the mechanical composition of these three soils.

TABLE I.

Soil No.	Sand.	Silt.	Clay (particles) below 0.002 mm.
P. C. 13	23.55 %	20.65 %	53.30 %
P. C. 72	4.52	49.75	44.08
P. C. 123	6.20	10.60	83.20

The soils were leached with 0.05N-HCl exhaustively to remove the exchangeable bases and then washed with distilled water until free from chlorides.

FIG. 1.

Titration curves of H-soil prepared from P.C. 13.

FIG. 2.
Titration curves of H-soil from P.C. 72.

FIG. 3.
Titration curves of H-soil prepared from P.C. 123.

Figures 1-3 give the titration curves of the H-soils, thus obtained, with hydroxides of Na, K, Ca and Mg and show that the soils differ widely as regards their behaviour towards bases.

(ii) The H-soils, obtained above, were converted to manganese soils by treating 50 g. portions with a litre of normal manganese chloride solution according to Prince and Toth (*loc. cit.*). The soils were then washed free of chlorides.

(iii) To 5 g. portions of the manganese soils, hydroxides of Na, K, Ca and Mg were added separately in increasing amounts. In this way sets of manganese soils containing varying amounts of each one of the four bases and having different p_H values were obtained. The soils were shaken with distilled water for 48 hours before subjecting them to electro dialysis.

Equipment and Technique of the Method used for Electro dialysing Soils.

The electro dialysis of soils was carried out for 5 hours at 100 milliamp. current in an apparatus fitted with a rotating anode and a cone-shaped cathode made from thick platinum gauze. Formerly (Puri and Hoon, *loc. cit.*; *Soil Sci.*, 1938, 45, 309) a copper cone served as the cathode. It was, however, found that on electro dialysing manganese soils some material was deposited on the cathode and the filter paper holding the suspension. In this investigation it was therefore considered necessary not only to determine the manganese content of the electro dialysate but also of the deposit on the cathode etc.

The electro dialysate was titrated with standard HCl using phenolphthalein as indicator and then manganese was determined by the bismuthate method (*Imp. Bureau Soil Sci. Bull.*, 1937, No. 17). The deposit on the cathode and filter paper (after washing off the soil suspension) was dissolved in dilute H_2SO_4 and its manganese content determined separately as in the electro dialysate. The amount of manganese actually removed by electro dialysis of soils is represented by the total of the manganese determined in the electro dialysate and the deposit on the cathode etc.

The p_H of 1:5 soil-water suspensions, given in the tables was determined by the glass electrode (Hoon and Taylor, *Memoir Punj. Irri. Res. Inst.*, 4, No. 1).

It was considered of interest to determine the manganese content of artificially prepared manganese soils by different methods and compare the results. The manganese content of the soils, prepared from the three soils

described under (a) (ii) prior to the addition of the hydroxides of Na, K, Ca and Mg was determined by the following methods:

- (i) Directly from the manganese soils by bismuthate method.
- (ii) Leaching the soils with neutral ammonium acetate and estimating manganese in the leachates.
- (iii) Subjecting the soils to electro dialysis and determining manganese in the electro dialysate and the deposit on the cathode, etc. separately. The results are given in Table II.

TABLE II.

Manganese content of artificially prepared manganese soils by different methods.

Manganese soil prepared from soil No.	pH of 1:5 soil-water suspension.	Total manganese content (direct).	Manganese in N. ammonium acetate leachate of soils.	Mn recovered by electro dialysis in 5 hr.		
				in the elec. tro dialysate. (A)	deposited on the cathode. (B)	(A + B)
P. C. 13	3.62	63.75 m. eq.	44.60 m. eq.	10.9 m. eq.	10.6 m. eq.	21.5 m. eq.
P. C. 72	4.80	41.75	35.80	11.6	11.9	23.5
P. C. 123	4.14	31.80	22.40	20.8	10.6	31.4

DISCUSSION.

The results show that whereas in manganese soils prepared from P. C. 13 and P. C. 72, only a portion of the total manganese could be recovered on electro dialysing for 5 hours, the amount being even less than that recovered by leaching the soils with normal ammonium acetate solution, almost the whole of manganese was recovered by electro dialysis from manganese soil prepared from P. C. 123. These differences in the recovery of manganese from the three soils are rather significant. In manganese soils, prepared from P. C. 123, the recovery of manganese by electro dialysis is quick and almost complete in 5 hours under the conditions of the experiment. With manganese soils prepared from P. C. 123 and P. C. 72, however, the recovery of manganese is a much slower process.

TABLE III.

Electrodialysis of soils artificially prepared from P.C. 13.

Base added to the manganese soil.	pH of 1:5 soil-water suspension.	Manganese recovered by electro-dialysis from soils.			Recovery of the other base.
		Mn present in the electro-dialysate.	Mn present in the deposit.	Total.	
Mn-Na soils.					
4.0 m. eq.	5.49	8.40 m. eq.	15.60 m. eq.	24.00 m. eq.	52.5 %
10.0	7.29	4.50	9.60	14.10	80.0
26.0	8.18	5.60	8.20	13.80	89.2
50.0	10.12	14.50	—	14.50	82.4
100.0	11.00	15.20	—	15.20	70.9
Mn-K soils.					
4.0	5.31	7.00	15.40	22.40	75.0
10.0	6.80	4.70	12.70	17.40	79.0
26.0	8.29	6.10	11.90	18.00	85.7
50.0	9.60	3.00	3.40	6.40	78.6
100.0	10.08	4.40	3.40	7.60	94.0
Mn-Ca soils.					
15.0	5.62	14.80	17.60	32.40	35.3
20.0	6.56	9.70	9.90	19.60	33.5
25.0	6.86	11.80	7.10	18.90	48.4
37.0	7.26	3.80	4.50	8.30	44.0
50.0	7.82	5.40	1.90	7.30	40.0
90.0	8.55	5.10	2.10	7.20	45.4
Mn-Mg soils.					
10.0	5.80	8.70	5.00	13.70	3.0
30.0	6.34	5.10	16.20	21.30	3.3
60.0	7.33	2.00	18.90	20.90	5.16
140.0	8.25	2.30	19.60	21.90	4.40

TABLE IV.

Electrodialysis of artificially prepared soils from P. C. 123.

Base added to the manganese soil.	pH of 1.5 soil-water suspension.	Manganese recovered by electrodialysis.			Recovery of the other base.
		Mn recovered in the electro-dialysate.	Mn recovered in the deposit on the cathode.	Total.	
Mn-Na soils.					
4.0 m. eq.	6.30	16.60 m. eq.	—	16.60 m. eq.	100.0 %
20.0	7.76	10.00	6.00 m. eq.	16.0	100.0
30.0	9.14	11.40	2.60	14.0	100.0
50.0	9.90	12.20	3.80	16.0	100.0
100.0	10.14	9.80	2.00	11.80	94.3
Mn-K soils					
4.0	6.04	18.40	5.20	23.60	100.0
20.0	7.05	14.80	4.00	18.80	99.5
30.0	8.22	13.60	4.40	18.00	96.0
50.0	10.12	7.20	2.70	9.90	97.4
100.0	10.52	10.60	1.10	11.70	98.7
Mn-Ca soils.					
4.0	5.04	13.40	1.90	15.30	92.5
10.0	6.24	10.00	3.80	13.80	80.0
20.0	7.02	8.80	2.80	11.60	79.0
70.0	8.47	7.10	1.40	8.50	80.42
100.0	9.09	6.10	2.60	8.70	78.80
150.0	9.76	3.30	2.10	5.40	64.47
Mn-Mg soils.					
10.0	5.24	6.30	11.10	17.40	38.0
30.0	6.80	9.10	7.30	16.40	21.0
50.0	7.70	5.40	10.50	15.90	20.6
80.0	7.90	6.00	8.60	14.60	19.25
150.0	8.15	5.00	8.60	13.60	14.0

TABLE V

Electrodialysis of artificially prepared soils from P.C. 72.

Base added to the manganese soil.	pH of 1:5 soil-water suspension.	Manganese recovered by electro dialysis.			Recovery of the other base.
		Mn recovered in the electro-dialysate.	Mn deposited on the cathode.	Total.	
Mn-Na soils.					
4.0 m. eq.	7.40	12.20 m. eq.	4.60 m. eq.	16.80 m. eq.	97.5 %
10.0	8.56	9.80	2.80	12.60	100.0
20.0	9.06	7.80	4.40	12.20	97.0
50.0.	11.10	8.80	1.00	9.80	95.2
100.0	11.25	7.50	2.00	9.50	99.8
Mn-K soils.					
4.0	7.10	9.20	4.60	13.80	100.0
10.0	7.90	10.50	5.20	15.70	100.0
20.0	9.20	6.80	2.80	9.60	100.0
50.0	11.45	3.00	0.20	3.20	94.4
100.0	11.90	5.00	0.40	5.40	97.7
Mn-Ca soils.					
10.0	7.48	11.20	7.00	18.20	80.0
20.0	8.30	8.50	2.80	11.30	86.0
30.0	9.00	6.60	6.20	12.80	90.0
50.0	9.96	5.10	6.50	11.60	89.8
100.0	10.54	4.30	6.40	10.70	83.6
Mn-Mg soils.					
10.0	6.60	10.60	10.60	21.20	24.0
30.0	7.22	9.40	11.50	20.90	22.0
50.0	7.65	8.60	12.40	21.00	15.0
70.0	7.80	6.60	16.00	22.60	13.15
120.0	8.20	1.20	19.40	20.60	15.75

Tables III-V give the percentage recoveries of manganese and the second base, on electro dialysis, from Mn-Na, Mn-K, Mn-Ca and Mn-Mg

sets of soils of varying p_H values prepared as described before (a, iii). There are again certain differences in the total manganese recovered from the various sets prepared from the three soils which are analogous to the differences obtained with pure manganese soils (Table II). There are, however, certain fundamental differences in the recovery of manganese in the electrolysate and the deposit in the different sets of soils. The differences observed may be considered under the following heads.

Recovery of Manganese in the Electrolysate.

(i) The maximum recovery of manganese in the electrolysates is obtained from the Mn-Na sets of soils and on the whole there is a tendency for greater recovery of manganese with increase in p_H value.

(ii) The Mn-K and Mn-Ca sets of soils behave somewhat similarly and in these the recovery of manganese decreases as the p_H increases.

(iii) The recovery is a minimum in the Mn-Mg sets of soils.

Recovery of Manganese as Deposit.

(i) The deposit obtained on electrolysing Mn-Na sets of soils contains the least amount of manganese and there is a tendency for the amount of manganese present in the deposits to decrease with increase in p_H value. Mn-K sets of soils behave in a similar manner to the Mn-Na sets.

(ii) The Mn-Ca sets of soils behave in a peculiar way. There is a decrease in the manganese content up to about p_H 8.0 after which there is again a slight increase.

(iii) In the Mn-Mg sets of soils the major portion of the manganese recovered by electrolysis is present in the deposit portion.

It may be concluded from the foregoing that at high p_H values when the dominant base in the exchange complex is sodium more manganese comes out in the soluble form. With increase of the lime status of soils, on the other hand, the amount of manganese which comes in solution is greatly reduced.

Electrolysis of Natural Soils.

The recovery of manganese from natural soils on electrolysis was examined. A few soils from good and bad areas containing different amounts of total manganese were electrolysed for 5 hours under conditions similar to those for artificially prepared manganese soils. Manganese was determined separately in the electrolysate recovered in the first hour and the collective electrolysate of the next four hours. This was done to obtain some idea as to the rate of recovery of manganese from these

soils. The manganese contents of the two portions were added together to obtain the total recovery during five hours and its percentage on the total manganese present in the soils calculated. The results are given in Table VI.

TABLE VI.

Percentage recovery of manganese from natural soils by electro dialysis.

Reg. No. of soil.	Total manganese content.	p_H .	Manganese recovered from soil by electro dialysis.			Electrodialy- sable and total manganese.
			1st hour.	Next four hours.	Total in 5 hours.	
Good soils.						
1290	0.75 m. eq.	7.98	Nil	Nil	Nil	—
1291	1.05	7.94	Nil	Nil	Nil	—
1308	1.30	7.77	0.05 m. eq.	Nil	0.05 m. eq.	3.84 %
Bad soils.						
513	4.00	10.46	0.20	Nil	0.20	5.0
514	4.00	10.44	0.20	0.05 m. eq.	0.25	6.25
515	3.40	10.40	0.10	0.05	0.15	4.41
516	2.70	10.28	0.20	Nil	0.20	7.41

The results show that soils having high p_H values (and also high manganese contents) yield more manganese on electro dialysis than soils with low p_H values (and low manganese contents). Moreover the major portions of the electro dialysable manganese comes in the first hour of electro dialysis.

It is not surprising, therefore, that in soils of high p_H values more manganese might come out in the soluble form and thus be made available to plants. This availability of manganese may be reduced when the dominant base in the exchange complex of soils is calcium.